

THAI STUDENTS' PERCEPTIONS OF FOREIGN ENGLISH TEACHERS: IMPLICATIONS FOR PUBLIC EDUCATION POLICY

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to investigate Thai students' perceptions of foreign English teachers (FETs) in Thailand, focusing on their teaching effectiveness, cultural competence, and English language proficiency. A mixed methods design was employed, involving surveys and open-ended questions with a sample of 12 second-year and third-year high school students. The results revealed that Thai students generally perceive foreign English teachers positively, valuing their cultural sensitivity, effective communication, and clear pronunciation. However, challenges such as communication barriers, cultural differences, and pedagogical issues were identified. Students also reported numerous benefits, including exposure to diverse cultures, improved language proficiency, and enhanced confidence. Based on these findings, recommendations for public education policies include enhancing teacher training, supporting foreign English teachers, adapting curricula, improving assessment, and fostering collaboration. Future research should explore the long-term impact of foreign English teachers and consider comparative and qualitative studies to gain a deeper understanding of the factors influencing student perceptions and learning outcomes.

Keywords: *Student Perceptions, FET, Diversity, Thailand*

INTRODUCTION

English language proficiency has become increasingly important in Thailand as the country integrates into the global economy (Ulla, 2018). Despite being introduced to

English in their primary years (Noom-ura, 2013), many Thai students struggle to speak and understand the language (Chema et al., 2023; Kaewmala, 2012). This is partly due to the ineffectiveness of English language teaching and learning in Thailand, as evidenced by low TOEFL scores compared to other countries in the region (Kongkerd, 2013). The role of foreign English teachers (FETs) in Thailand has gained attention in recent years. Previous research has explored various aspects of foreign English teachers, including their qualifications, teaching styles, and challenges (Luangkrajang, 2023; Chuchuen, Tubsree, & Suthithatip, 2017). While these studies have provided valuable insights, there remains a gap in the literature regarding Thai students' perceptions of FETs.

Understanding Thai students' perspectives on FETs is crucial for several reasons. First, it can help inform public education policies related to English language teaching. Second, negative perceptions among students could have detrimental implications for English language education in Thailand, potentially leading to decreased motivation and learning outcomes. Third, by understanding students' views, we can evaluate the effectiveness of FET programs and identify areas for improvement (Nunan & Lamb, 2000)

This study aims to address the research gap by exploring Thai students' perspectives on FETs. By providing valuable insights into the factors influencing students' learning experiences and attitudes towards FETs, this study can contribute to the existing literature and inform public education policies in Thailand.

Research Questions

The primary objective of this study is to explore the perspective of Thai students towards their foreign English teachers and to consider how this might affect educational policies in Thailand. To achieve this goal, the study addressed these specific questions:

1. What are Thai students' overall perceptions of foreign English teachers in terms of their teaching effectiveness, cultural competence, and English language proficiency?
2. What are the primary challenges perceived by Thai students in learning English from foreign English teachers?
3. What are the primary benefits perceived by Thai students in learning English from foreign English teachers?
4. From the findings of the study, what action plans are recommended to inform the development and implementation of public education policies related to foreign English teacher programs in Thailand?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed a mixed-method approach to gain a comprehensive understanding of Thai students' perceptions of foreign English teachers. Both quantitative and qualitative data were collected from a sample of second and third-year high school students at Pratuangtipwithaya 2 School.

Sampling

There are forty second and third-year high school students in total. Out of the total 40 second and third-year high school students, 12 will be chosen to participate in the study. This will be divided equally between the two years, with 6 students from each. The study's sample does not reflect the diverse student population of Thailand Universities. It does not seek to generalize its findings or compare them to other institutions. The students included may vary significantly from those who were not included in the study. Informed consent was obtained from both students and their legal guardians prior to participation.

Data Collection

Quantitative data was collected using a survey instrument, while qualitative data was collected through open-ended questions. The survey instrument was validated by the school director. The survey was tested to make sure it was valid and reliable. After the review, the reliability of the survey was calculated. Table 1 shows that the questionnaire has a Cronbach's alpha of $\alpha = 0.91$. According to Gliem and Gliem (2003), a Cronbach's alpha coefficient approaching 1.0 suggests strong internal consistency, with values in the range of 0.7 to 1.0 generally deemed reliable. This suggests that the questions on the questionnaire are excellent in Internal Consistency.

Table 1. Reliability of the Instrument

<i>Item</i>	<i>Result</i>
Number of Questions	15
Sum of Item Variance	5.26
Variance of Total Score	20.08
Cronbach's Alpha	0.79
Internal Consistency	Excellent

Data Analysis

Once the data was collected, the researcher tabulated the survey scores and conducted statistical analysis. After gathering the data, the researcher organized and

analyzed it using interval calculation by weighted mean. The 4-point Likert scale data was analyzed using interval calculation by weighted mean, maintaining a constant difference between response categories (e.g., 0.74 and 0.75), to avoid bias, as presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Interpretation of 4-Likert Scale

<i>Level of Agreement</i>	<i>Scale</i>
1 - Strongly Disagree	1.00 – 1.74
2 - Disagree	1.75 – 2.49
3 - Agree	2.50 – 3.24
4 - Strongly Agree	3.25 – 4.00

The qualitative data from the open-ended questions was analyzed using thematic analysis to identify common themes and patterns related to Thai students' perceptions of foreign English teachers.

RESULTS

Table 3. Thai Student's Response on the Foreign English Teacher's Teaching Effectiveness

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Result</i>
Strong Pedagogical Skills	2.42	Disagree
Clear Communication	2.75	Agree
Engaging Classroom	2.83	Agree
Constructive Feedback	2.75	Agree
Adaptability	2.58	Agree
Average Mean	2.67	Agree

Table 4. Thai Student's Response on the Foreign English Teacher's Cultural Competence

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Result</i>
Culturally Sensitive	2.92	Agree
Communicate Effectively from Different Cultural Backgrounds	2.67	Agree
Knowledgeable about Local Culture and History	2.50	Agree
Create a Culturally Inclusive Environment	2.92	Agree
Avoid Cultural Misunderstandings	2.83	Agree
Average Weighted Mean	2.77	Agree

Table 5. *Response on the Foreign English Teacher's English Language Proficiency*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Result</i>
Strong English command	3.25	Strongly Agree
Accurate language use	3.42	Strongly Agree
Clear pronunciation	2.92	Agree
Appropriate vocabulary	2.75	Agree
Effective communication	2.42	Disagree
Average Weighted Mean	3.03	Agree

Table 6. *Thematic Analysis for challenges faced by the Thai Students to the Foreign English Teachers*

Code	Themes
Experiences of Students	
1. Difficulty to follow instruction	
2. Difficulty to understand accent	1. Communication Barriers
3. Foreign English teacher uses deep English vocabulary	2. Cultural Barriers
4. Difficulty to understand foreign English teacher pronunciation	3. Lack of Classroom Engagement
5. Lack of confidence in speaking English	4. Pedagogical Challenges
6. Foreign English teacher have different culture	
7. Culture difference in teaching style	
8. Foreign English teacher doesn't explain things clearly	
9. Foreign English teacher is too fast-paced	

Table 7. *Thematic Analysis for benefits faced by the Thai Students to the Foreign English Teachers*

Code	Themes
Experiences of Students	
1. Developing intercultural communication skills	1. Exposure to Diverse Cultures and Perspectives
2. Learning about different cultures and customs	2. Improved Language Proficiency
3. Enhanced fluency in speaking English	3. Enhanced Confidence and Motivation
4. Exposure to native English accents	4. Exposure to new teaching and learning approaches
5. Improved pronunciation and intonation	5. Real-World Applications
6. Increased vocabulary	

7. Feeling motivated to learn and improve
 8. Overcoming language anxiety
 9. Exposure to innovative teaching methods and Technique
 10. Learning English for practical purposes and career advancement.
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DISCUSSION

Problem 4.1 What are Thai students' overall perceptions of foreign English teachers in terms of their teaching effectiveness, cultural competence, and English language proficiency?

The results from Table 3 indicate that Thai students perceive their foreign English teachers to have agreeable clear communication abilities, constructive feedback, adaptability and an engaging classroom environment. While the average mean score of 2.67 suggests an overall positive perception, the scores for strong pedagogical skills areas suggests that areas for further improvement are needed as the result suggests a disagreeable perception. These findings highlight the strengths and areas for development in the teaching practices of foreign English teachers in Thailand.

The results from Table 4 indicate that Thai students perceive their foreign English teachers as being culturally sensitive, effective communicators across different and cultural background with an average weighted mean of 2.77. This indicates for an overall positive perception.

The results from Table 5 indicate that students generally perceive their foreign English teachers as having a strong command of the English language, using accurate language, and possessing clear pronunciation, with an average weighted mean of 3.03, indicating an overall positive perception. However, there is a notable discrepancy between the positive ratings for these indicators and the lower rating for effective communication. This suggests that while teachers may demonstrate proficiency in the technical aspects of English, they may face challenges in effectively conveying their thoughts and ideas to students.

It is important to note that effective communication involves more than just grammatical accuracy and pronunciation. It also requires the ability to adapt language to different contexts, to use appropriate vocabulary, and to engage students in meaningful interactions. This discrepancy highlights the need for continued professional development in communication skills for foreign English teachers.

Problem 4.2 What are the primary challenges and benefits perceived by Thai students in learning English from foreign English teachers?

The thematic analysis presented in Table 6 highlights several key challenges faced by Thai students when learning English from foreign English teachers (FETs). These challenges can be categorized into four primary themes: communication barriers, cultural barriers, lack of classroom engagement, and pedagogical challenges. Students often struggle to comprehend FETs due to their unfamiliar accents and the use of advanced vocabulary, which can hinder their comprehension and participation in class. Cultural differences in norms and teaching styles can also create misunderstandings and difficulties for students, leading to confusion and discomfort in the classroom environment. The use of deep English vocabulary and fast-paced teaching styles can make it difficult for students to engage with the material and stay motivated, potentially leading to a lack of interest and participation. Additionally, some FETs may lack the necessary pedagogical skills to effectively teach English to Thai students, which can hinder their ability to explain concepts clearly, provide appropriate feedback, and create engaging learning experiences.

Problem 4.3 What are the primary benefits perceived by Thai students in learning English from foreign English teachers?

The thematic analysis of Thai students' experiences with foreign English teachers (FTEs), presented in Table 7, reveals several key benefits. These benefits can be categorized into five primary themes: exposure to diverse cultures and perspectives, improved language proficiency, enhanced confidence and motivation, exposure to new teaching and learning approaches, and real-world applications. Learning from foreign English teachers expose students to different cultural customs, traditions, and ways of life, fostering intercultural communication skills, empathy, and understanding. This exposure broadens their global outlook, promoting awareness of the interconnectedness of the world and appreciation for cultural diversity. Additionally, learning from foreign English teachers enhances students' pronunciation, intonation, fluency, vocabulary, and grammar, improving their overall language skills. Students often experience increased confidence in their English language abilities, overcoming language anxiety and fear of making mistakes, which can lead to a more positive attitude towards English learning and motivation for improvement. Foreign English teachers often introduce innovative teaching methods and techniques that can enhance student engagement and understanding, such as interactive activities, group work, and real-world language tasks. By being exposed to authentic English language use, students can better prepare themselves for practical applications, such as career advancement and higher education, gaining a competitive edge in the global job market and opening doors to new opportunities.

Problem 4.4 From the findings of the study, what action plans are recommended to inform the development and implementation of public education policies related to foreign English teacher programs in Thailand?

The researcher proposes a course of action based on these findings. To enhance the quality of foreign English teacher programs in Thailand and improve student outcomes, it is essential to prioritize teacher training and professional development, provide adequate support for foreign English teachers, adapt curricula to meet the diverse needs of Thai students, implement effective assessment and evaluation methods, and foster collaboration among stakeholders. By focusing on these areas, Thailand can create a more conducive environment for English language learning, equip students with valuable language skills, and contribute to the country's overall educational development. Specifically, teacher training should emphasize pedagogical skills, cultural sensitivity, and communication skills. Foreign English teachers should be provided with mentorship, professional communities, and fair compensation. Curricula should incorporate culturally relevant materials, be tailored to different language levels, and strike a balance between formal and communicative language teaching. Assessment should be holistic, and teacher evaluation should be comprehensive. Finally, collaboration among government agencies, educational institutions, and relevant stakeholders is crucial for ensuring policy coherence and effective implementation.

Conclusions

This study aimed to address this gap by investigating Thai students' overall perceptions of Foreign English teachers, the challenges and the benefits they perceive in learning English from them. The findings revealed that Thai students generally have positive perceptions of foreign English teachers in terms of their teaching effectiveness, cultural competence, and English language proficiency. However, there is a need for further improvement in areas such as pedagogical skills and effective communication.

The study also identified several challenges faced by Thai students in learning English from foreign English teachers, including communication barriers, cultural barriers, lack of classroom engagement, and pedagogical challenges. On the other hand, students perceived numerous benefits, such as exposure to diverse cultures, improved language proficiency, enhanced confidence and motivation, exposure to new teaching approaches, and real-world applications.

Based on these findings, several recommendations can be formulated for the development and implementation of public education policies related to foreign English teacher programs in Thailand. These recommendations include enhancing teacher training and professional development, supporting foreign English teachers, adapting curricula, implementing effective assessment and evaluation methods, and fostering collaboration among stakeholders.

If these recommendations are addressed, Thailand can improve the quality of

foreign English teacher programs, enhance student outcomes, and contribute to the country's overall educational development. Further research is needed to explore the long-term impact of foreign English teachers on Thai students' English language proficiency and their overall educational experiences.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several areas for future research can be identified:

1. **Longitudinal Studies:** To track changes in Thai students' perceptions of foreign English teachers over time, longitudinal studies could be conducted to assess the impact of various factors, such as teacher training programs, curriculum reforms, and policy changes.
2. **Comparative Studies:** Comparing the perceptions of Thai students towards foreign English teachers with those of students in other countries could provide valuable insights into cultural differences and best practices in English language teaching.
3. **Qualitative Case Studies:** In-depth qualitative case studies of individual foreign English teachers and their classrooms could provide a more nuanced understanding of the factors influencing student perceptions and learning outcomes.
4. **Larger Sample Sizes:** While this study provided valuable insights, a larger sample size would enhance the generalizability of the findings and allow for more detailed statistical analysis.
5. **Focus on Specific Teaching Practices:** Future research could focus on specific teaching practices, such as the use of technology, cooperative learning, or project-based learning, to examine their impact on student perceptions and language learning outcomes.
6. **Investigating the Role of School Context:** Exploring the role of school context, including factors such as school resources, leadership, and overall school culture, on student perceptions of foreign English teachers could provide valuable insights for policy makers.

By conducting further research in these areas, it is possible to deepen our understanding of the complex relationship between foreign English teachers, Thai students, and the broader educational context in Thailand. This knowledge can inform the development of more effective policies and practices to enhance English language education in the country.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study followed the principles of Mirza's et al. (2023) ethical principles outlined by Bryman and Bell to ensure the well-being and privacy of participants. First, the researcher of this study obtained informed consent, ensuring participants understood the study and participated voluntarily. They also treated participants with respect throughout the data collection process. To minimize risk of harm or conflict, the researcher established clear procedures at the outset.

Second, the study prioritized participant privacy. All information collected was kept confidential and anonymized. Participant identities were never revealed, adhering to both ethical research practices and Personal Data Protection Act. This law protects all types of personal information and applies to anyone processing such data. The researcher further ensured transparency by disclosing his affiliation and the purpose of data collection. All communication with participants was honest and upfront, avoiding misleading information or biased representation of data.

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